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Voicing the Trauma of Women in the Short Stories of Temsula Ao

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Abstract Northeast India has always been a mystery. There are arguments that there is nothing called a “North- Easterner” as the concept is purely geographical, it is an extremely heterogeneous cluster of people and there exists no common history and heritage of the people in North East India as a whole. Indeed, as an aftermath of the colonial rule, there is interplay of power politics, evident even in the literature produced. Women writing is not alien from it. Due to inherent restrictions women has always emerged as the victim. TemsulaAo, the Naga voice strongly represented the trauma of these victims as being suppressed, uneducated, illiterate not emancipated and under privileged. The ‘Laburnum for my head’and ‘These hills called home’ elaborates the plight of women under the lens of psychosocial impact. Although some of the stories have self- confidant and assertive empowered female characters but they are undermined. This paper explores the experience of Ao,who showed the path of half- baked dreams, unfulfilled promises and suppressed desires of the marginalized. She tries to capture the experience of postcolonial nation that facesonset of many new concepts. The presentation of insurgency in the stories of these two books explicitly establishes Ao as a true story teller giving her reader only ample space to develop their own reading the text. Love, hostility, salacity, familial relations, extra marital relations, rape, aborticide, pregnancy out of wedlock are the celebrated themes from the point of view of female characters. Life of women in a patriarchal society, their aspiration and their perspective of survival is aptly picturized by the writer.Thus, this paper critically analyses the true facet of trauma of women through the eyes of Ao.

Keywords Trauma, Psychosocial,Patriarchal, Insurgency.

Introduction Northeast India, a region surrounded by three valleysand interspersed with a number of mountain ranges, acquires a mysterious and remarkable position in geography of India. The Blue hills including the eastern Himalayas on the North, the Naga hills on the East, the Mizo and Tripura hills on the south and the Shillong plateau (named in the 1930s by the Indian geographer, S.P. Chatterji, as Meghalaya) on the West, form almost completely natural boundaries of the Brahmaputra valley, the heartland of Assam. For several centuries the valleys and hills of Northeast India have been unveiled toinvasion and migration later on under the captivity of mainland India felt aligned. The construction of northeast as the binary ‘other’ in the pre and post-colonial times brings a latentthreat to their culture, identity and literature. The memory of the pangsof the suffering reached its apex during the days of armed conflict. The sense of being disownedfrom fair representation in the manifestation of great Indian civilization or even in the nationalist parlance has deeply affected the literatiof the regions of Northeast India in the post-independence era. “Perceptions of the traumatic expression of a people living in the midst of terror and fear and yet cherishing hopes that human values will triumph some day and a new dawn of peace would emerge out of this trial by fire.”(Misra X) Northeast literature is the pulpit of the people’s trauma and suffering. The voice of Northeast writers is the collective voice of people who had been exploited, neglected and alienated in their own

territory. Before reading the traumatic experience of women characters of Temsula, it is essential to comprehend what trauma is.

Objective of study

This paper analyses the true facet of trauma of women through the eyes of Ao.

Review of Literature

According to American Psychological Association, "Trauma is an emotional response to a terrible event like an accident, rape or natural disaster. Immediately after the event, shock and denial are typical. Longer term include unpredictable emotions, flashbacks, strained relationships and even physical symptoms like headache or nausea."

Main Text

Of course, Temsula Ao, the well-known contemporary Northeast writer who emerged from the state of Nagaland, reflects this kind of victimization. Being a native of the area she writes with a very realistic and practically firsthand account of what is happening there. Because she is unafraid to capture the social and political upheavals of Nagaland in her creative universe, her works are epochal. Anywhere these kinds of upheavals happen, one figure that is part and parcel of this surrounding has always emerged as victim i.e. Women. Temsula has justified the plight of this binary of society in her works.

My objective is to show their traumatic predicament in the region through a nuanced study of the two selective works of the popular Naga writer Temsula Ao, thus analyzing the identity of women in ethnic society. On the whole, it will be an exploration of how Temsula Ao uses her literary works with a motive to revive the inner strength of female aspect under the threat of violence and insurgency by depicting their experiences. Through her writing, Ao portrays women who are weak and helpless before their circumstances. However, there are other examples that emphasize independent, astute, kind and highly respected women. Additionally, their physical and mental suppression has the upper hand. Women are shown as being subjected to two forms of oppression. Such a woman's status depresses her. Because of her status as someone who is twice removed from the aristocracy and patriarchy in her culture, she believes that these women are hushed, suppressed and subjugated. She has sensibly illustrated the inherent limitations placed upon them by the patriarchal system in addition to the tortures and hardships of insurgency.

In the two collections of stories, she crafts her tales with skills. There are plenty of stories in these collections where she highlights the female quotient. A widow's blinding longing for a laburnum tree is shown in the opening narrative of the book, 'Laburnum for my head'. The entire plot revolves around her "epiphanic sensation" of having a laburnum tree planted at her tomb, as well as her boldness and self-confidence in the face of the patriarchal system. How she manages the familial situation after her husband's demise, how she firstly breaks the custom by going in the funeral, her befriending her driver Babu and executing the secret plan of growing laburnum on her grave finding a suitable spot for grave by satisfying Town committee, pacifying the family with deft and crafty manipulation of her knowledge and lastly being successful in blossoming luxuriant Laburnum, all these events are so craftily woven by Ao that somewhere it undermines the qualities of women as self-effacing and being submissive. "So ends the story of the undramatic life of an ordinary woman who cherished one single passionate wish that a humble laburnum tree should bloom once a year on her crown" (20)

The prologue of the story "Three Women" introduces the audience to a special triad of mother daughter relationships. In this particular narrative, Ao develops into a skilled storyteller. It senses the generation lineage of grandmother (Lipoktula), mother (Medemla) and daughter (Martha). The story portrays not only the intense emotion of motherhood but also Medemla's loss of love, Lipoktula's burden of previous secrets and rape guilt and Martha's illegitimate pregnancy. Through the passionate dialogues of these three women characters Ao peeps into the psyche of women in reference to love marriage parenthood, genetic appearance, career, social atrocities, suppressed sexual desires etc. Martha, the daughter is perplexed with her genetic appearance and the victim of identity crisis throughout the story. "But the word 'Coolie' had stuck in my mind and one day I asked them, "Why do you call me 'Coolie'? The one called Chubala said, "Don't you know that you do not belong to our village and that Medemla is not your real Mother? Haven't you ever wondered why you look so different from us? You speak just like we do but it is not your language. Our mothers have always known this and they told us." (64) The intense desire of physical response is justified by Martha in her case of illegitimate pregnancy. "I looked at her pained expression and wondered; how could one describe the response of a woman's body to the touch of a man she loved to such a person as my mother, who never had felt the demanding power of such love? And harder still, convince her that once you've tasted love like that, there was no stopping?" (77) The sudden jerk felt by Medemla, the mother at the rejection of her love is traumatized in Medemla's History: "After receiving terrible letter from Imsutemjen- I

still cannot describe the feeling of rejection and betrayal that seemed to incinerate me, reducing to nothingness.”(67)The trauma of rape and suppressed sexual desire is picturized through the character Lipoktula (grandmother) in Lipoktula’s Secret: “Why had I not resisted more vigorously, screamed or even scratched his face when he was groping for my sex?”(74) “I could not explain my own conduct. I made a momentous decision; I would remain silent.”(75) “But each time, I only recall how contagious the crazed passion of the man was and how an explicable reaction of my body turned my feeble resistance to participatory submission.”(79)This is the tale of three generations of women connected by a horrific secret that comes full circle and alters not just the life of the woman but also that of her daughter and granddaughters. Turning towards Freud’s theories on traumatic experience and memory, we can sense the childhood abuses and identity crisis of Martha, pangs of rejection to Medemla and Lipoktula’s earlier experience of sexual assault that are part of their unconscious memory.

In the story “Sonny” Aodepicts the beloved’s unfulfilled love, which is a hidden tragedy. Between Sonny and his lady love, the specter of his last-ditch commitment to the elusive ‘cause’ had loomed like a black cloud. When Sonny had stealthily vanished from his lady love’s life and entered a different realm. Her obsessive love for a man who valued his own passion more than a woman’s love sent her into a deep well of self-doubt and self-accusation. “Sonny dead was something incomprehensible; what I had cherished and kept alive in my innermost being was the image of ‘Sonny alive’ the way I had remembered him all these years; vibrant and so full of hope. If it had been difficult to live a desolate life without him then, now I felt truly bereaved, more than ever before, though he had been out of my life there last twelve years.” (89) She feels marooned on a stark landscape after parting with his love. She has the memories alive of their formal farewell night having a note by Sonny, “Sweetheart this is not goodbye because you will forever be the love of my life”(91) Ironically the note that has exclamation of eternal love proves doggerel when she hears the news of marriage of Sonny with one of the female cadres in his outfit. “...If I ever really hated the man I had loved so much, it was at this moment. (93) Hearing the news of death of Sonny. I finally wept the inconsolable lament of the truly bereaved and cried until there were no more tears to shed for the man I had lost twice once to his idealism and now to death. (94)

Temsulagives her reader access to Freud and Breuer, who write:

“We may reverse the dictum *cessante causa cessat effectus* (“when the cause ceases the effort ceases”) and conclude from these observations that the determining process (that is, the recollection of it) continues to operate for years ---- not directly, through a chain of intermediate causal links, but as a directly releasing cause – just as psychological pain that is remembered in waking consciousness still provokes a lachrymal secretion long after the event. Hysterics suffer mainly from reminiscences.” (1955:7)

The process of remembering penalizes the psychological pain but also impute value to a previously repressed experience in the unconscious. Temsula makes an effort to follow up with the people whose sufferings have not yet been acknowledged or spoken about. In her other collection “These hills called home: Stories from a war zone” she vehemently brings out the horror brutality, the cruel and bloody dimensions of war. The first story of the collection, ‘The Jungle Major’ which although narrates the insurgency and its consequences on the lives of villagers but somewhere between the lines it also spots the issues of mismatched marriage, pain of rejection, acceptance of fate in marriage institutions and childlessness. Khatila, the beautiful and clever woman has managed herself in the mismatched marriage with Punaba. The childless state of the couple became an issue such as; “Just as the initial announcement of their marriage had produced adverse reactions, now their childless state became the subject of many lewd comments and absurd speculations.”(2) Later on in the story the reader came to know about the rescue of Punaba through Khatila’s presence of mind.

While war and conflict damage and devastate society at all levels women’s experience can be devastating on a wholly different level when women’s bodies become the soft target for reprisals from armed personnel, so is in the story “The Last Song”. It was the women who suffered a lot in those days. The story powerfully depicts how women and children are treated during the operation. Apenyo, the young girl and gifted singer became a victim to the Army captain and- “he grabbed Apenyo by the hair and with a bemused look on his face dragged her away from the crowd towards the old church building.” (28) Aofurther delineates the insane act of armed forces in the story as; “The young captain was raping Apenyo while a few soldiers were watching the act and seemed to be waiting for their turn.(28)The frantic situation of daughter being raped crazed the mother but later on she herself met the same fate. The scenes of the insane act give goosebumps to the reader and fills the heart with shame and disgust. But the savagery was not over the captain ordered to burn out that place so that the evidence of his despicable act be wiped off. Thus, this was Apenyo’s last song.

The term 'ethical responsibility' is used by GayatriChakravertySpivakto describe the situation in which we have a deep indulgence with someone and get response from both sides. Then 'an embrace, an act of love' happens but sometimes this embrace may be unrequited as the differences and distances are too great. By considering the term and concept of Spivak we see that the girl, Imnala in the story 'The Night' is also a prey of unrequited love not once but twice. 'The Night' is a tale describing the fate of Imnala and her illegitimate second pregnancy. Imnala was the victim of betrayed love and got pregnant by the man who earlier promised to marry her but later on disappeared for he had to train himself as a soldier in China to join the underground army. The worst humiliation happened with the girl when the man refused to acknowledge the child as his own in village meeting. This was the bitter experience of 4 years ago but now she is more aggrieved with her second pregnancy which is also out of wedlock. This time the young man Repalemba, the partner of her father in road construction work is the father of the unborn child. The girl and her family are perplexed at night before the day when the fate of the baby in her womb would be decided. On such occasions the trauma of a woman is indescribable as she feels entangled mentally, emotionally and socially. Here Tamsula provides some insight into the predicament of woman in Naga cultural society. It looks into how a woman's identity is shaped and influenced by her maternal condition, the disparate cultural, social and political institutions which control their daily existence from which they learn to constantly negotiate the pressure of living in male dominated societies. In 'The Night' we have minute details of proceeding in village meetings:

"On such occasions, village custom gave the aggrieved party a lot of leeway: to hurl abuses including physical assault within a reasonable limit, and imposition of a fine in cash or kind. Most important of all, the fate of the unborn child would be determined on that day, depending on the admission or denial of parentage by the man involved."⁽⁴⁶⁾ There were instances where under similar circumstances a girl's hair was chopped off and her clothes stripped off to shame her.⁽⁵⁵⁾ A woman who is suppressed under social customs and patriarchy have to engulf all the sorrows and Imnala is not an exception of this. "Now she recalled what her mother used to say: Remember in our society a woman must have the protection of a man even if he happens to be blind or lame. A woman alone will always be in danger."⁽⁵³⁾ Her fate hung in the balance, she would have to face and bear the scorn and abuse of Alemba's wife and the censure of society whose balance of justice always tended to tilt against the woman. A married man was equally guilty, but today she would be the sole accused.⁽⁵⁴⁾

Conclusion We are therefore in awe of Tamsula's storytelling abilities. Despite the fact that her works may draw inspiration from real life experiences or events, she retains the creative freedom that comes with writing fiction. Creative writers have the responsibility of giving voice and expression to women's pain, suffering, rage, aspirations, dreams and ambition. "Traumatic experience beyond the psychological dimension of suffering it involves, suggests a certain paradox: the most direct seeing of a violent event may occur as an absolute inability to know it; that immediately, paradoxically may take the form of belatedness."^(Caruth92) In these story collections of Ao we learn about the traumatic lives of women. She skillfully captures the perplexing experience of women caught in a cycle of violence because of empathy for the plight of women. The various forms of violence and socio-political events that are forcing the women in the area to live traumatised lives on a physical and psychological level are subtly revealed in Ao's narratives. Ao presents her reader a plethora of emotive sentiments by allowing her characters to voice out their plight. The efforts to give exposure to unmentioned and unacknowledged pain is quite successful here.

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